

Advances in Measurement of Shear and Friction of Woven Fabrics for Forming

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SUMMARY

Fabrics provide a challenge to the standard materials characterization methods used to generate input properties for forming simulations. This paper addresses recent advances in measurement of shear and friction properties, along with insights gained from studies of dry fabric, commingled fabrics, and fabric-reinforced sheet moulding compound.

Keywords: Woven fabric, Shear, Friction, Forming, Drape

INTRODUCTION

Variations on forming of woven fabrics have been explored as a rapid method of fabricating structural composite parts. Woven fabric reinforcements provide both structural properties and formability. While the forming behaviour of fabrics can be non-intuitive to users more familiar with metal stamping and polymer injection moulding, current advances in modelling are strengthening the ability to predict manufacturing defects such as wrinkling, yarn breakage or spreading, and bridging. Such forming simulations require the correct representation of the material properties, but fabrics also provide a challenge to standard materials characterization methods and interpretations. For woven fabrics, shear is the primary mode of deformation, while friction between the tool and the fabric and inter-ply friction can also be a governing factor in generation of defects.

For woven fabrics, significant progress has been made over the past several years, in large part due to an international benchmarking exercise on materials characterization and simulation of composite sheet forming [1]. Shear characterization has mainly focused on trellis-frame (picture-frame) or bias extension tests. Friction characterization has seen variations on heating and pullout methods. This paper discusses the impact of multiple test and material variations – for example, side yarn removal in the shear specimen, specimen size, and viscosity change during the test – on the interpretation of the material properties. A companion paper addresses the effect of these material representations on the forming simulations.

Trellis (Shear) Frame Characterization

The trellis frame, or picture frame, setup (Figure 1) for measuring the evolving shear modulus of fabrics has been widely studied. Past researchers have noted the effect of fabric placement in the fixture on the shear response. The discrete nature of the yarns and the potential for discontinuous stress and strain fields -- e.g., due to significant variations in yarn tensions -- can lead to incorrect interpretations of the shear modulus from the shear load-angle curves. One factor is the difference between the shear angle calculated from the crosshead and the local shear angle. New measurement techniques with sufficiently high resolution and full-field measurement capability enable the direct measurement of local shear angles and strains. An example is the shear angle map shown in Figure 2. This image was obtained using an Aramis digital image correlation system. Such techniques provide greater insight into the effect of test specimen variability on the measurement of shear loads. The shear angle results shown in Figure 3 are for a specimen where there was good correlation between the Aramis measurements of the central region and the calculation based on crosshead displacement.

Figure 1. Example of Shear Frame Characterization

Figure 2. Example of Aramis Digital Image Correlation Measurements of Shear Angle in Shear Frame Testing

Figure 3. Correlation of Center Region Shear Angle Measurements from Shear Frame Tests

Friction Characterization

Friction testing presents challenges due to the sensitivity to variations in the tool-fabric interface. Figure 4 is a schematic of the current friction test setup, which allows control of normal force, pullout rate, and tool temperature. Studies on dry fabrics, commingled glass/PP fabrics, and fabric-reinforced sheet molding compound (SMC) have demonstrated the effects of resin film layer, viscosity, pullout rate, and other parameters on the friction response. Figure 5 shows an example of the effect of pullout rate on the friction coefficient. This paper will discuss the relevance of traditional friction models such as Stribeck theory to capture the correct representation of fabric-resin systems.

Figure 4. Friction Test Setup

Figure 5. Friction Coefficient Measurement for Commingled Twill Weave

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